

An innovative lens-based imaging detector for GRAIN in SAND at the DUNE Near Detector complex

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The Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE)

The DUNE experiment is a new generation long-baseline neutrino oscillation experiment

DUNE main physics goals:

- ❖ Establish whether nature **violates CP** in the lepton sector and if so **measure** δ_{CP} ,
- ❖ Improve accuracy on θ_{23} and determine the octant $\theta_{23} < \pi/4$ vs $\theta_{23} > \pi/4$,
- ❖ Determine the **neutrino mass ordering** at high confidence level.

Astrophysics via MeV-scale ν_e s at Far Detector:

- ❖ Supernova pointing and neutrino property measurement via SNB detection,
- ❖ Solar neutrino measurements of *hep* flux, 8B channel and Δm_{21}^2 .

- ❖ **Beyond Standard Model** (Light Dark Matter, proton decay, sterile neutrinos...)

DUNE Near Detector

- The ND measures the **unoscillated** ν_μ and ν_e (and **antineutrino**) **spectra** produced at Fermilab.
- The ND constrains systematics by measuring **flux**, **cross sections** and **detector response**.
- ND data predict FD spectra, testing PMNS framework, **mass ordering** and **CP violation**.
- To meet DUNE precision, the ND must outperform the FD in key measurements.
- The ND also supports SM cross-section measurements and searches for new physics.

[«The SAND tracking system at the DUNE Near Detector»](#)

DUNE Near Detector -- overview

[«The DUNE experiment»](#)

SAND: System for on-Axis Neutrino Detection

- **SAND** is a permanently on-axis, multi-purpose detector with:
 - 0.6T superconducting magnet;
 - Electromagnetic calorimeter (ECal);
 - **GRAIN**: a LAr active target (~ 1 ton), with imaging system
 - A low density tracker

Renovated from KLOE experiment

«A Straw Tube Tracker for Neutrino Physics»

SAND goals

- **Monitor beam** changes continuously with high significance on a weekly basis;
- Constrain **nuclear effects** by using different nuclear targets (Ar, CH₂, C);
- Perform independent $\nu/\bar{\nu}$ flux measurements;
- BSM physics program

TOP

SIDE

«The SAND detector of the DUNE experiment»

GRAIN: GRanular Argon for Interactions of Neutrinos

GRAIN can be considered both as a **passive** and **active** target.

PASSIVE

- 1-ton LAr in a magnetized volume;
- To study for ν -Ar interactions with downstream tracker/calorimeter

ACTIVE

It will be instrumented with sensors:

- For collecting UV scintillation light with arrays of SiPMs
- For performing imaging of the event

[«GRAIN: a novel liquid argon detector for imaging of neutrino interaction in the DUNE near detector»](#)

[«Imaging neutrino interactions with Liquid Argon scintillation light at the DUNE Near Detector Complex»](#)

Main motivations:

- **Constraint on systematics** for the ν -Ar cross-section and nuclear effects;
- **Complementary Ar target** for cross-calibration with other ND detectors

Innovative imaging system for GRAIN

- Each spill shows **charged tracks emerging from SAND interactions**, with ≈ 0.1 interaction in GRAIN.
- The current design is **based on imaging the LAr scintillation light**:
 - Charged particles produce VUV photon ($\lambda = 127$ nm).
 - **Pixelated photon detectors**, immersed in LAr and equipped with focusing optics.
 - Two optical technologies are under evaluation for the focusing system:

1) UV lenses

[«Imaging systems for the liquid Argon target of SAND at the DUNE Near Detector Complex»](#)

2) Coded aperture masks

[«Imaging systems for the liquid Argon target of SAND at the DUNE Near Detector Complex»](#)

- Refractive index matched to LAr, high UV transparency
- **Sensor-lens distance < 10 cm**
- **Two plane convex fused-silica lenses (Ø 60 mm), 2 mm spacing**
- Focal length 88.8 mm in LAr
- Efficient light collection up to **~130 cm**

Event view

LEFT camera

Optimal focus is achieved for **distances between 40 cm and 1.5 m** between tracks and lens.

At distances < 40 cm the image becomes defocused.

TOP camera

BOTTOM camera

RIGHT camera

Tracks inside GRAIN

Samples: 20k ν_μ CCQE interactions in the whole GRAIN volume

The lengths have been calculated inside GRAIN.

A track is visible if its image on the sensor is longer than 10 pixels.

≈72% of the muon tracks is **visible**

≈22% of the proton tracks is **visible**

Reconstruction

Tracks and vertices can be reconstructed in the 3D volume by using two methods:

- **Image-based method**

- **Voxel-based method**

Track visibility and number of cameras per track

Number of cameras vs MC track length

Out of 23,394 visible tracks, 19,670 were successfully reconstructed, corresponding to a **reconstruction efficiency of ~84%**.
A track is considered reconstructable if it's seen in at least 2 cameras

This plot shows that a visible track is seen by **~11 cameras** at the same time.
The mean value of the length of a visible track is 25 cm.

Vertex and endpoint reconstruction

➤ Image-based method

VERTICES

ENDPOINTS

Conclusions

- DUNE will address open questions in neutrino physics through the combined operation of its Near and Far detector systems
- SAND serves as a robust beam monitor, enabling complementary measurements of both the flux normalization and its energy dependence, which are crucial for controlling systematic effects in long-baseline analyses
- GRAIN will enhance SAND physics program and is able to provide an additional sample of neutrino interaction in LAr
- A prototype of the lens based optical detector is under test in Genoa
- Initial studies based on simulation are promising

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

BACKUP SLIDES

Lens-based optical detector

Geometry for lens configuration: 53 cameras

Material constraints

- They must have a **suitable refractive index** relative to LAr, and remain **highly transparent** at the relevant wavelengths.

Adopted optical concept

- The design uses a **gas-filled gap** between surfaces to create the necessary refractive-index contrast with LAr.
- Optical module includes:
 - A **multi-element lens system**;
 - A **light-shield/support structure**;
 - A **SiPM matrix** on a front-end board.

Design requirements

- Track images must have a thickness **< 5-6 mm** to separate multiple high-energy tracks;
- A **wide field of view** is needed to maximize fiducial coverage;
- Lens size must guarantee **sufficient photon statistics** across the FoV;
- Sensor-lens distance must remain **< 10 cm**.

Final lens configuration

- Two **plane-convex fused-silica lenses** (Corning HPFS 8655), 60 mm effective diameter, curvature radius 79 mm, separated by 2 mm.
- Material provides **>99.6% transmittance** above 170 nm and refractive index 1.6.
- Focal length is **88.8 mm** assuming $n(\text{LAr}) = 1.26$ at 178 nm.
- Lens diameter allows efficient light collection up to **~130 cm** from the optical plane.

Simulation chain

- The performance of GRAIN internal reconstruction on ν -Ar events is studied by simulating samples of neutrino interactions in its LAr volume.
 - Only single neutrino events have been considered

Track direction reconstruction – residuals

Out of 23394 visible tracks, 19669 are reconstructed. For track angle reconstruction, two methods are used:

- 1) **Endpoint method** → reconstruction is successful in 10989 cases ($\approx 55\%$ of cases)
- 2) **Voxel fit method** → reconstruction is successful in 18660 cases (94% of cases)

Track direction reconstruction – residuals – 2

Since the M1 method fails when the vertex is not reconstructed, I use the M2 method to obtain the track direction and then recover the vertex from it. This improves the M1 reconstruction performance, increasing the success rate from **55%** to **93%**.

Out of 23394 visible tracks, 22164 should be reconstructed and 19669 are reconstructed (valid endpoint). For track angle reconstruction, two methods are used:

- 1) **Endpoint method** → reconstruction is successful in **10361+7826** cases ($\approx 93\%$ of cases)
- 2) **Voxel fit method** → reconstruction is successful in 18660 cases (94% of cases)

New geometry – lens configuration

Item	Old geometry	New geometry
Total cameras	38	53
Side cameras	28	32
Top row	5	14
Bottom row	5	7
Camera length	10 cm	14 cm
GRAIN x	1000 mm	1500 mm
GRAIN y	1456 mm	1478 mm
GRAIN z	475 mm	487 mm

#cameras detecting the same track simultaneously

Old geometry: ~7 cameras record the same track simultaneously

New geometry: ~11 cameras record the same track simultaneously

→ Clear improvement!